

UISS-TB-DR qualification advice

The Universal Immune System Simulator – Tuberculosis model (UISS-TB) is an In Silico Trial technology with a sophisticated, bi-dimensional agent-based simulator encompassing multi-scale and multi-organ perspectives. This model simulates the proliferation of a specific Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB) strain within the pulmonary compartment, considering the immune system's response and the impact of potential treatments aimed at curbing bacterial growth or enhancing the immune reaction.

On 25/09/2022, the applicant Mimesis S.r.l., on behalf of the In Silico World Consortium, requested advice from EMA on how to qualify the Universal Immune System Simulator – Tuberculosis Disease Model (UISS-TB) as a drug development tool.

On November 22nd, 2022, the applicants had a preliminary informal meeting with the appointed Qualification team.

The Briefing Book was subsequently resubmitted in its modified version, and the procedure started on the 11th of April, 2023.

On the 31st of July 2023, EMA sent the applicants a list of issues.

After submitting the response to the issues document, a discussion meeting with the EMA Qualification Team took place on September 25th, 2023, where the issues and the proposed answers were discussed.

On the 21st of December 2023, the EMA Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use adopted the advice to be given to the Applicant. The complete documentation of the qualification advice is available in the folder “UISS-TB - Public Domain Documents”.